

Recycling subcontinental plagioclase-bearing lower crust in the North China craton

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Figure S1. (a) Concordia plots of LA-ICPMS U-Pb zircon analytical results for the Mengyin HMAs (sample MMY06-2) (Ling et al., 2009). The $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ age is used for zircons older than 1000 Ma, while the $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ age is used for younger ones. Zircon grains spot with a spot size of 32 μm . (b) Comparison of zircon age distribution between Mengyin HMAs and North China Archaean-Palaeoproterozoic basement (Gao et al., 2004). (c–e) Two episodes of the North China crustal thickening, reworking and recycling tied to rapid spreading of the Pacific plate during the Mesozoic. Note that the Pacific plate rapidly spread at 155–175 Ma and 120–130 Ma simultaneously with two pulses of high-Mg andesites and granitoids in the eastern North China, and the second pulse may play a more role in driving lithospheric gravitational instability. Data sources: spreading rate for the Pacific plate (Bartolini and Larson, 2001; Conrad et al., 2011); Xinglonggou HMAs (Gao et al., 2004); age spectra of granitoids and zircon age spectra of lower crustal xenoliths in the eastern North China are after Zhang et al. (2014).

Figure S2. Sr-Nd isotopic compositions of the Mengyin high-Mg andesites (calculated at 128 Ma), Fangcheng basalts (125 Ma) and their hosted pyroxenite xenoliths from Zhang et al. (2007); Feixian alkaline basalts (119 Ma) from Gao et al. (2008); Archean cratonic mantle from Xu et al. (2008) and Gao et al. (2008); Depleted mantle (DM) from Salters and Strack (2004). The Sr-Nd isotope compositions of lower continental crust (LCC) are reconciled by the average of the Yinan adakitic granites (124 Ma) in Shandong, North China (Zhang et al., 2014).

Figure S3. (a) Density of hydrous melt as a function of H₂O fraction in melt (wt%). (b-f) Density contrast between mafic granulite and asthenosphere (solid peridotite + hydrous melt) as a function of H₂O fraction in melt (wt%). Model for calculating the density of hydrous silicate melts is after Ueki and Iwamori (2016). Data sources: melt compositions from North China (Zhang et al., 2017).

Table S1. Zircon U-Pb age data for Mengyin high-Mg andesite (sample MMY06-2)

Analysis	$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$		$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{235}\text{U}$		$^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$		Th (ppm)	U (ppm)	Th/U	$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$		$^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$		$^{207}\text{Pb}/^{235}\text{U}$	
	Ratio	1 σ	Ratio	1 σ	Ratio	1 σ				Age (Ma)	1 σ	Age (Ma)	1 σ	Age (Ma)	1 σ
MMY01-15	0.052	0.002	0.141	0.004	0.020	0.000	154	300	0.52	297.5	68	124.6	1.4	133.7	3.7
MMY01-9	0.050	0.001	0.137	0.002	0.020	0.000	120	681	0.18	210.7	41	126.1	1.2	130.5	2.1
MMY01-6	0.050	0.003	0.136	0.007	0.020	0.000	82	96	0.86	178.7	118	126.4	1.7	129.1	6.3
MMY01-5	0.049	0.002	0.135	0.005	0.020	0.000	149	246	0.61	167.9	88	126.7	1.5	128.9	4.6
MMY01-4	0.049	0.002	0.134	0.004	0.020	0.000	165	372	0.44	136.0	74	126.8	1.4	127.3	3.8
MMY01-11	0.072	0.003	0.199	0.009	0.020	0.000	73	213	0.34	998.9	94	127.0	1.9	184.1	7.8
MMY01-20	0.050	0.002	0.137	0.006	0.020	0.000	83	113	0.73	175.5	104	128.2	1.6	130.7	5.6
MMY01-14	0.049	0.001	0.135	0.004	0.020	0.000	78	229	0.34	132.3	65	128.6	1.4	128.8	3.4
MMY01-8	0.050	0.001	0.139	0.003	0.020	0.000	372	681	0.55	199.0	50	128.8	1.3	132.5	2.7
MMY01-16	0.048	0.001	0.136	0.003	0.020	0.000	177	345	0.51	117.9	55	129.7	1.3	129.1	2.8
MMY01-21	0.049	0.002	0.138	0.005	0.020	0.000	153	262	0.58	136.7	89	130.6	1.6	131	4.7
MMY01-23	0.049	0.003	0.144	0.008	0.021	0.000	108	185	0.58	163.3	121	135.3	1.9	136.9	6.7
MMY01-18	0.050	0.002	0.174	0.006	0.025	0.000	94	137	0.69	180.6	83	161.2	1.9	162.5	5.4
MMY01-19	0.114	0.001	5.209	0.057	0.332	0.003	61	124	0.50	1862	21	1846	15	1854	9.4
MMY01-22	0.149	0.002	9.010	0.090	0.437	0.004	161	219	0.73	2339	18	2338	18	2339	9.1
MMY01-3	0.167	0.002	10.802	0.114	0.470	0.005	45	143	0.31	2524	19	2484	19	2506	9.8
MMY01-25	0.164	0.002	10.757	0.117	0.474	0.005	64	110	0.58	2502	19	2502	20	2502	10
MMY01-13	0.167	0.002	10.954	0.113	0.475	0.005	145	124	1.18	2532	18	2503	19	2519	10
MMY01-1	0.165	0.002	10.891	0.106	0.478	0.005	136	211	0.65	2512	17	2516	20	2514	9.1
MMY01-10	0.162	0.002	10.671	0.109	0.478	0.005	68	104	0.65	2476	18	2517	20	2495	9.5
MMY01-7	0.159	0.002	10.518	0.101	0.478	0.005	166	1081	0.15	2500	17	2520	20	2482	8.9
MMY01-24	0.182	0.003	12.879	0.229	0.513	0.006	4	10	0.39	2671	30	2670	26	2671	17
MMY01-12	0.180	0.002	12.946	0.148	0.521	0.005	94	291	0.32	2654	20	2704	22	2676	11
MMY01-17	0.260	0.003	23.400	0.233	0.654	0.006	80	126	0.64	3244	17	3243	24	3244	9.7

Table S2. Geochemical and isotopic compositions of Mengyin high-Mg andesites (Ling et al., 2009)

Sample	MMY-10	MMY-11	MMY-12	MMY-13	MMY-14	MMY-15	MMY-16	MMY-17	MMY-18	MMY-19	MMY-20
SiO ₂	55.45	56.12	55.01	55.66	55.39	55.38	52.51	52.32	55.59	53.28	55.97
TiO ₂	0.94	0.91	0.96	0.90	0.91	0.87	0.97	0.98	1.11	1.00	0.85
Al ₂ O ₃	16.24	16.14	16.32	16.11	16.10	15.55	14.79	14.72	15.21	14.76	15.10
TFe ₂ O ₃	5.28	5.73	5.82	6.59	6.27	7.25	8.81	8.82	5.55	7.46	5.71
MnO	0.13	0.10	0.11	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.09	0.06
MgO	5.13	4.91	5.31	5.09	4.84	5.70	6.98	7.01	5.41	6.79	5.01
CaO	7.33	7.47	6.88	6.86	6.85	6.97	9.00	9.10	7.75	7.73	6.55
Na ₂ O	3.18	3.18	3.03	3.15	3.19	3.30	2.77	2.79	3.32	3.04	3.63
K ₂ O	3.01	3.02	3.29	3.03	3.25	3.01	2.09	2.08	3.27	3.02	3.67
P ₂ O ₅	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.51	0.51	0.49	0.47	0.46	0.67	0.65	0.73
LOI	2.34	1.98	2.45	2.41	2.14	1.01	1.11	1.12	1.54	1.69	2.26
Total	99.53	100.06	99.69	100.39	99.53	99.62	99.61	99.51	99.54	99.51	99.54
Mg#	65.8	62.9	64.4	60.5	60.5	60.9	61.1	61.2	65.9	64.3	63.5
Cr	174	183	174	170	135	197	207	205	264	274	147
Ni	68.8	63.8	72.4	63.9	63.2	78.0	66.1	67.3	115	109	85.2
Sr	1159	1113	1066	1166	1113	1195	1042	1025	1283	1236	1584
Y	21.0	19.9	19.6	22.8	19.6	19.5	20.8	21.1	20.4	23.1	20.9
Zr	248	249	240	239	242	234	169	168	287	258	276
Nb	13.4	13.2	12.9	13.3	13.2	12.7	10.2	10.2	16.3	14.8	14.7
Cs	0.36	0.62	0.35	0.28	0.51	0.62	0.36	0.32	1.09	0.64	0.52
Ba	1417	1451	1328	1427	1361	1522	1045	1026	1563	1570	1716
La	78.3	78.2	76.2	83.4	79.1	80.0	52.8	53.1	111	100	127
Ce	159	150	147	162	152	161	115	113	215	199	238
Pr	16.5	16.5	15.8	16.7	16.3	17.3	12.7	13.0	22.4	22.1	25.3
Nd	62.9	59.8	59.1	64.2	63.1	61.9	51.9	52.5	82.3	80.3	100.0
Sm	9.70	9.17	9.07	10.1	9.20	9.53	8.52	8.61	11.9	11.9	13.8
Eu	2.47	2.34	2.36	2.41	2.29	2.35	2.20	2.23	2.92	2.95	3.36
Gd	8.64	8.74	8.07	9.37	8.64	9.11	8.22	8.16	11.0	10.8	11.9
Tb	0.98	0.94	0.88	0.96	0.89	0.92	0.87	0.87	1.03	1.14	1.11
Dy	4.11	4.18	4.02	4.25	4.31	3.92	4.15	4.55	4.95	5.01	4.76
Ho	0.74	0.69	0.68	0.76	0.69	0.67	0.76	0.79	0.76	0.80	0.68
Er	1.93	1.97	1.87	2.03	1.97	2.02	2.11	2.20	2.14	2.27	1.93
Tm	0.25	0.23	0.23	0.27	0.25	0.27	0.27	0.30	0.26	0.30	0.23
Yb	1.51	1.46	1.47	1.58	1.40	1.49	1.65	1.70	1.47	1.68	1.36
Lu	0.21	0.22	0.20	0.26	0.21	0.22	0.24	0.23	0.22	0.23	0.16
Hf	4.91	5.16	5.18	5.11	5.11	5.01	3.94	4.00	6.46	5.55	5.66
Ta	0.62	0.62	0.59	0.63	0.63	0.62	0.49	0.50	0.82	0.73	0.70
Tl	0.11	0.16	0.15	0.099	0.13	0.19	0.072	0.060	0.20	0.16	0.20
Pb	13.4	12.3	12.4	13.6	13.7	16.5	9.12	8.47	14.4	14.5	17.5
Th	9.27	9.62	10.0	10.5	10.1	8.68	4.82	5.40	12.8	9.86	14.0
U	1.24	1.30	1.56	1.44	1.18	1.83	1.39	1.24	2.64	2.32	1.60
Eu/Eu*	0.82	0.80	0.84	0.76	0.78	0.77	0.80	0.81	0.78	0.79	0.80
Sr/Y	55	56	54	51	57	61	50	48	63	54	76
La/Yb	52.0	53.7	51.7	52.8	56.5	53.8	32.1	31.2	75.8	59.9	93.6
⁸⁷ Sr/ ⁸⁶ Sr	0.711133	0.711310	0.711278	0.711097			0.709319		0.711686	0.710521	0.710720
2σ	2	2	2	2			2		2	2	2
¹⁴³ Nd/ ¹⁴⁴ Nd	0.511755	0.511758	0.511754	0.511755			0.511861		0.511756	0.511879	0.511821
2σ	1	2	1	1			2		1	1	1
⁸⁷ Rb/ ⁸⁶ Sr	0.143	0.189	0.168	0.139			0.14		0.191	0.181	0.13
¹⁴⁷ Sm/ ¹⁴⁴ Nd	0.0933	0.0926	0.0927	0.0951			0.0992		0.0874	0.0898	0.0833
T _{DM} (Ga)	1.76	1.75	1.75	1.79			1.71		1.68	1.56	1.55
I _{Sr}	0.710910	0.711014	0.711016	0.71088			0.709100		0.711387	0.710238	0.710517
ε _{Nd} (t)	-15.8	-15.7	-15.8	-15.8			-13.8		-15.7	-13.3	-14.4

Note: Major oxides are reported in weight percent (wt%), trace elements in parts per million (ppm).

Table S3. LA-ICP-MS elemental analytical data for olivine and clinopyroxenes from the Mengyin HMAs

Mineral Note Profile	Type I zoned clinopyroxene (normally zoned)					
	core			→		rim
	spot 1	spot 2	spot 3	spot 4	spot 5	spot 6
SiO ₂	51.5	50.9	50.4	50.0	49.5	48.7
TiO ₂	0.31	0.42	0.57	0.77	0.90	1.16
Al ₂ O ₃	1.64	2.07	2.45	2.45	2.64	2.80
FeO	4.93	5.60	6.79	8.18	8.99	10.2
MnO	0.14	0.15	0.17	0.21	0.22	0.26
MgO	18.2	17.6	16.6	15.9	15.4	14.0
CaO	22.6	22.6	22.1	21.6	21.4	21.4
Na ₂ O	0.25	0.29	0.36	0.34	0.35	0.44
K ₂ O	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.06
P ₂ O ₅	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.43
Total	99.6	99.6	99.5	99.4	99.5	99.4
V	183	236	253	368	435	584
Cr	968	963	1383	1253	908	418
Co	34.0	34.5	36.9	39.8	41.4	41.9
Ni	194	183	138	106	83.0	49.2
Rb	0.06	1.63	0.29	0.00	0.00	1.07
Sr	77.4	83.4	95.6	91.0	88.2	117
Y	11.0	15.0	16.9	24.1	27.7	42.7
Zr	10.1	19.9	29.3	43.0	48.1	73.9
Nb	0.02	0.07	0.09	0.12	0.13	0.40
Cs	0.03	0.09	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.04
Ba	0.41	3.27	7.70	4.69	1.35	39.0
La	1.88	3.08	5.75	7.87	9.16	29.2
Ce	8.76	12.9	22.0	30.4	34.8	83.9
Pr	1.82	2.62	4.03	5.67	6.82	13.9
Nd	9.71	16.0	24.3	33.0	37.8	67.9
Sm	3.48	4.29	6.18	8.43	10.6	14.3
Eu	0.85	1.13	1.68	2.09	2.34	3.60
Gd	3.31	3.96	4.59	6.64	8.22	13.5
Tb	0.37	0.56	0.57	0.96	1.05	1.59
Dy	1.83	2.82	3.47	5.23	5.76	9.13
Ho	0.45	0.53	0.60	1.05	1.19	1.66
Er	1.11	1.82	1.70	2.42	2.88	4.35
Tm	0.13	0.25	0.22	0.27	0.37	0.55
Yb	0.72	1.32	1.23	1.80	1.87	3.26
Lu	0.09	0.14	0.23	0.28	0.31	0.58
Hf	0.57	0.87	1.11	1.85	2.32	3.45
Ta	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Pb	0.16	0.32	0.37	0.31	0.20	1.51
Th	0.16	0.32	0.37	0.31	0.20	1.51
U	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.07	0.06	0.66

Table S3 Continued

Minerall	Type II zoned clinopyroxene (reversely zoned)												
	Note	rim	←	mantle	mantle	core	core	core	core	mantle	mantle	→	rim
Profile	spot 1	spot 2	spot 3	spot 4	spot 5	spot 6	spot 7	spot 8	spot 9	spot 10	spot 11	spot 12	spot 13
SiO ₂	47.4	48.66	50.81	49.58	47.92	48.70	48.13	49.93	50.15	47.71	47.61	47.70	47.58
TiO ₂	0.88	0.61	0.27	0.32	0.80	0.60	0.66	0.50	0.56	0.58	0.88	1.02	0.98
Al ₂ O ₃	3.04	2.21	1.82	2.41	4.16	3.56	4.03	3.12	3.22	3.81	3.31	3.46	3.47
FeO	10.4	8.14	5.14	5.32	7.68	7.11	7.29	7.45	6.56	6.00	8.58	9.67	9.15
MnO	0.25	0.21	0.15	0.13	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.16	0.13	0.20	0.22	0.21
MgO	14.6	17.0	18.2	17.6	16.2	17.1	17.1	16.6	17.3	16.9	16.0	15.3	15.6
CaO	21.3	22.3	22.7	23.6	22.1	21.8	21.7	21.4	20.9	23.7	22.5	21.6	22.0
Na ₂ O	0.51	0.26	0.24	0.27	0.42	0.34	0.36	0.34	0.39	0.31	0.33	0.37	0.36
K ₂ O	0.30	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
P ₂ O ₅	0.77	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.07	0.05
Total	99.4	99.47	99.30	99.20	99.46	99.35	99.45	99.54	99.24	99.2	99.4	99.4	99.4
V	431	261	132	149	253	229	267	248	255	236	359	443	417
Cr	428	1319	3229	3840	1389	2323	1523	963	3117	3797	1691	914	1350
Co	40.4	39.5	36.4	35.0	35.8	38.9	39.6	41.4	38.9	34.2	39.0	40.4	39.0
Ni	76.3	123	179	175	141	179	178	173	183	171	105	93.4	108
Rb	4.40	0.058	0.226	0.00	0.018	0.00	0.986	0.432	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.01	0.16
Sr	141	76.2	69.1	85.3	120	87.6	98.0	83.5	82.1	99.6	95.4	113	112
Y	35.8	16.4	6.69	6.79	17.6	13.3	14.2	13.2	11.3	11.5	20.9	26.9	24.8
Zr	44.5	27.6	7.95	9.47	41.9	26.8	32.7	26.5	35.0	25.0	42.8	50.2	52.8
Nb	0.12	0.000	0.038	0.017	0.052	0.020	0.205	0.042	0.008	0.00	0.13	0.12	0.05
Cs	0.04	0.020	0.000	0.004	0.008	0.008	0.000	0.092	0.038	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.01
Ba	0.28	0.26	0.00	0.84	0.09	0.77	22.42	0.23	0.99	0.33	5.88	9.74	10.66
La	46.4	4.95	1.62	1.88	6.66	4.23	5.08	4.16	3.78	3.47	7.59	11.87	9.16
Ce	107	18.94	6.64	6.95	26.12	15.70	17.08	14.79	15.15	12.75	27.44	39.07	33.1
Pr	14.43	3.35	1.27	1.37	4.52	2.71	2.98	2.66	2.77	2.25	4.84	6.54	5.91
Nd	67.8	20.14	8.31	8.09	26.77	17.73	19.10	17.84	16.57	15.08	29.8	39.40	33.0
Sm	14.49	5.28	2.17	2.50	6.56	4.86	4.94	4.49	4.38	3.93	7.02	9.00	7.56
Eu	2.78	1.39	0.63	0.72	1.67	1.15	1.21	1.14	1.06	1.07	2.03	2.29	2.12
Gd	10.40	4.89	2.09	2.05	5.90	4.57	4.60	4.06	4.06	3.40	6.68	7.76	7.40
Tb	1.28	0.64	0.29	0.30	0.75	0.47	0.54	0.50	0.46	0.49	0.85	1.05	0.94
Dy	7.25	3.57	1.53	1.70	3.92	2.89	3.41	2.80	3.21	2.62	4.50	5.33	4.94
Ho	1.35	0.62	0.20	0.31	0.65	0.38	0.54	0.59	0.70	0.48	0.89	0.98	1.01
Er	3.11	1.44	0.89	0.65	1.72	1.16	1.27	1.32	1.46	1.13	1.99	2.51	2.36
Tm	0.44	0.23	0.10	0.10	0.19	0.14	0.19	0.18	0.13	0.14	0.21	0.31	0.29
Yb	2.61	1.28	0.51	0.36	1.17	1.05	1.16	1.02	1.16	0.92	1.50	2.19	1.84
Lu	0.44	0.16	0.092	0.049	0.19	0.16	0.19	0.14	0.12	0.10	0.19	0.23	0.26
Hf	1.74	1.24	0.44	0.52	1.76	1.36	1.42	1.15	1.51	1.21	1.82	2.36	2.19
Ta	0.01	0.006	0.008	0.008	0.011	0.010	0.016	0.005	0.037	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.03
Pb	4.07	1.21	0.67	0.00	1.06	0.46	2.87	1.47	10.96	4.53	1.03	0.82	1.05
Th	1.42	0.058	0.00	0.004	0.036	0.079	0.173	0.050	0.032	0.04	0.09	0.15	0.09
U	0.19	0.010	0.00	0.00	0.013	0.00	0.025	0.006	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02

Table S3 Continued

Mineral	Type III zoned clinopyroxene						Type IV unzoned cpx		
	spot 1	spot 2	spot 3	spot 4	olivine inclusion		cpx-1	cpx-2	cpx-3
Profile	core	→		rim	core	rim	core	core	core
Note									
SiO ₂	51.0	49.1	48.1	49.2	38.6	40.0	50.04	48.1	49.6
TiO ₂	0.32	0.99	1.25	0.71	0.02	0.11	0.91	0.98	0.80
Al ₂ O ₃	1.88	3.79	4.49	3.85	0.02	0.41	2.85	2.95	2.40
FeO	4.32	5.96	6.87	6.33	20.2	20.5	10.45	9.17	9.56
MnO	0.11	0.14	0.15	0.13	0.31	0.33	0.27	0.22	0.24
MgO	18.2	16.4	15.2	15.6	39.9	37.1	16.02	16.0	16.0
CaO	22.8	22.4	22.5	23.4	0.18	0.34	18.27	21.7	20.3
Na ₂ O	0.40	0.51	0.55	0.30	0.01	0.03	0.40	0.38	0.36
K ₂ O	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.00
P ₂ O ₅	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.02
Total	99.1	99.3	99.2	99.5	99.2	99.1	99.24	99.5	99.2
V	108	188	214	250	5.57	20.0	470	471	376
Cr	5070	2735	3362	1389	60.3	173	260	720	907
Co	29.7	30.9	33.8	35.5	181	168	48	41.5	46.5
Ni	227	193	195	106	1339	1336	94	98.0	107.8
Rb	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.01	23.5	0.0	0.00	0.00
Sr	113	204	204	104	0.00	20.1	73.1	86.0	81.0
Y	7.89	22.1	27.0	16.7	0.43	1.02	27.3	26.8	20.4
Zr	17.5	88.4	115	37.0	0.53	14.0	46.6	45.2	40.0
Nb	0.01	0.35	0.37	0.00	0.02	1.04	0.16	0.04	0.09
Cs	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.04	0.00	9.63	0.02	0.00	0.00
Ba	0.04	0.39	0.52	0.43	0.35	134	0.59	1.00	7.00
La	4.32	16.8	19.3	5.12	0.04	6.09	6.29	7.94	7.52
Ce	14.8	57.2	66.2	19.5	0.03	11.8	29.2	31.3	29.0
Pr	2.68	9.59	11.4	4.21	0.09	1.09	6.09	5.76	5.36
Nd	14.6	50.6	60.5	22.0	0.17	3.60	37.6	32.5	33.7
Sm	3.68	11.8	14.7	5.81	0.00	0.14	10.2	7.89	8.63
Eu	0.96	3.20	3.56	2.08	0.00	0.19	2.25	1.89	2.15
Gd	2.56	8.35	10.5	4.90	0.00	0.71	7.64	7.07	6.73
Tb	0.39	1.00	1.21	0.64	0.01	0.00	1.03	0.97	0.81
Dy	1.74	5.11	5.97	3.82	0.07	0.11	6.19	5.29	4.70
Ho	0.34	0.94	1.05	0.52	0.03	0.08	0.86	1.08	0.88
Er	0.72	1.87	2.65	1.85	0.01	0.14	2.95	2.64	2.41
Tm	0.09	0.24	0.29	0.22	0.01	0.00	0.34	0.29	0.26
Yb	0.60	1.28	1.77	1.17	0.06	0.22	2.70	1.98	1.94
Lu	0.09	0.19	0.25	0.13	0.02	0.01	0.40	0.27	0.27
Hf	0.67	3.21	4.20	1.62	0.02	0.28	1.82	2.06	1.60
Ta	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.01
Pb	0.28	0.62	0.71	0.50	0.15	6.29	1.48	0.21	0.80
Th	0.28	0.62	0.71	0.50	0.15	6.29	0.04	0.09	0.07
U	0.03	0.22	0.23	0.04	0.00	0.35	0.00	0.01	0.00

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